

Tokenism: A cognitive dissonance reduction strategy for the general self-assessment of environmental responsible behaviour.

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Abstract.

Amidst growing environmental concerns, this study explores the psychological underpinnings of individuals' self-assessment of their general environmental behaviour. By analysing data from the 2023 Spanish General Social Survey, by the Centre for Sociological Research, we find that individuals' positive self-assessment of their environmental conduct is weakly correlated with specific pro-environmental actions, particularly those involving high costs. Conversely, it is found that specific behaviours that incur in low costs are the most significant determinants of individuals' positive self-assessment of their overall environmental behaviour. These results support the hypothesis that individuals engage in tokenistic behaviours as a means of reducing cognitive dissonance and maintaining a positive self-image as environmentally responsible.

Keywords.

Tokenism; Cognitive Dissonance; High-Cost Behaviours; Pro-Environmental Behaviours; Environmental Self-Assessment.

1. Introduction

The evidence of increasing environmental degradation is mounting. Global surface temperatures have risen by 1.1°C relative to pre-industrial levels during the decade of 2011-2020 (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2023). Similarly, the Living Planet Index (LPI) has reported a 73% decline in average wild populations over the past 50 years (World Wide Fund, 2024). Furthermore, an estimated 353 million tonnes of plastic waste was produced in 2019, with only 15% being recycled (OECD, 2022). Concurrently, various scenarios project a 10% reduction in global arable land by 2050 due to the adverse impacts of climate change (Campbell, 2022)

The mounting evidence of human activities' impact on the environment has led to growing scepticism about the viability of continuing with current growth patterns, even when guided by the principles of sustainable development (Latouche, 2009; Rosa, Dörre & Lessenich, 2017). Consequently, a growing number of scientists advocate for a fundamental shift in production and consumption patterns, replacing development-oriented goals with those that prioritize the preservation of collective survival conditions (Köhler et al., 2019).

Such shift necessitates substantial changes in lifestyles and individual behaviours, which must be aligned with the new demands of sustainability (Gaziulusoy & Oztenkin, 2019). This implies introducing a new range of behaviours aimed at mitigating environmental damage, but which are likely to entail a considerable number of inconveniences for

individuals. It is expected that a significant proportion of the behaviours that need to be introduced to mitigate environmental damage will be those that require individuals to bear greater costs and discomforts (Vieira, Castro & Souza, 2023).

However, numerous studies have highlighted the challenges individuals face in integrating these new behaviours into their lifestyles. Indeed, it is common to find warnings regarding the slow pace of adopting such behaviours, despite the rapid growth of environmental consciousness and pro-environmental attitudes (Venghaus, Henseleit & Belka, 2022). In this regard, it has been noted how individuals often seek to justify their inaction by referencing past environmentally responsible behaviours, thus feeling less obliged to engage in more demanding actions (Burger, Schuler & Eberling, 2022).

This paper aims to delve deeper into these issues. Specifically, it seeks to examine whether individuals who self-assessed a positive general environmental behaviour actually exhibited concrete and effective behaviours that led to genuine mitigation of existing environmental problems. Furthermore, it explores whether, in arriving at such a positive self-assessment of their behaviour, individuals considered behaviours that entailed lower costs and inconveniences, while neglecting more substantive and relevant behaviours, a strategy termed tokenism (Gifford & Chen, 2016). To address these objectives, this paper draws on a secondary statistical analysis of the questionnaire from the Spanish General Social Survey, Environment Module, conducted by the Centre for Sociological Research. The study employs descriptive, associative, and significance statistics, as well as logistic regressions.

2. Inconsistencies in environmentally responsible behaviours.

A well-documented phenomenon in environmental psychology is the disparity between pro-environmental attitudes and behaviours. Despite widespread support for environmental values, the corresponding adoption of environmentally responsible behaviours remains limited. This 'attitude-behaviour gap' (Broom, 2017) is evident across various contexts, including energy consumption (Fuchs & Lorek, 2010), fashion choices (Dhir et al., 2020), mobility behaviours (Lane & Potter, 2007), and sustainable consumption (Samarasinghe, 2012). In this regard, some studies identify correlations between environmental attitudes and behaviours (Xia et al., 2017; Leonidou, Leonidou, & Kvasova, 2010); however, the prevailing view is that such relationships are typically weak (Wright & Kljyn, 1998)

Research on the disparity between espoused values and actual behaviours has been extensively examined through cognitive dissonance theory. Developed by Leon Festinger in the 1950s, this theory suggests that discrepancies between an individual's cognitions create psychological discomfort, driving them to restore consonance (Festinger, 1957, 3). One such situation arises when individuals' cognitions about their behaviour, or its consequences, conflict with their underlying values or beliefs (Festinger, 1957).

Subsequent developments have modified some elements of the original theory, but have retained the mechanism of dissonance and the drive to restore consonance. For instance, it has been suggested that dissonance arises not so much from a conflict between cognitive elements but rather from a threat to self-esteem caused by a particular action (Greenwald & Ronis, 1978), or from a perceived undermining of one's moral character (Thibodeau & Aronson, 1992). Furthermore, it has been argued that

dissonance stems from a sense of violating the moral rules and values to which one adheres (Cooper & Fazio, 1984).

Cognitive dissonance theories have been applied to explain the documented gaps between environmentally responsible attitudes and behaviours, albeit partially (Schrems & Upham, 2020). In these cases, dissonance arises from the observable discrepancies between individuals' behaviours and their held values regarding appropriate environmental conduct, as suggested by Thøgersen (2004). Studies on cognitive dissonance stemming from the attitude-behaviour gap in environmental contexts have highlighted the difficulty of restoring consistency through shifts towards more sustainable behaviours (Bentler, Kadi, & Maier, 2023), making the readjustment of cognitive elements the more common response (Li, Agyewaah, & Zhao, 2023).

The literature has identified a range of cognitive strategies individuals employ to reduce or eliminate dissonance. These include avoiding thoughts that evoke awareness of their inconsistent behaviour (Rothgerber, 2020), lowering their standards for identifying behavioural inconsistencies (Menzies & Sheeshka, 2012; Ozaki, 2011), downplaying the consequences of maintaining unsustainable habits (Bosone, Chevrier, & Zenasni, 2022), perceiving others as engaging in even less sustainable behaviours (Diekmann and Preisendörfer, 1998; Schrems & Upham, 2020), believing they have reduced unsustainable behaviours even if they have not entirely ceased (Silva Souza & O'Dwyer, 2022), or anticipating future reductions in such behaviours (Scott, Kallis, & Zografos, 2019; Sedova, Slovak, & Jezkova, 2016). Other cognitive strategies for dissonance reduction involve emphasising the difficulties of changing one's behaviour (Gifford and Chen, 2017), or acknowledging the challenges of acting within conflicting value frameworks (Scott, Kallis, & Zografos, 2019). Additionally, recognising the limited individual capacity to significantly improve environmental problems through personal actions has been identified as a dissonance reduction strategy (Lorenzoni, Nicholson-Cole, & Whitmarsh, 2007; De Vos & Singleton, 2020)

One cognitive coping strategy for addressing cognitive dissonance related to environmental behaviours is tokenism. Initially developed in the context of inequality, tokenism theories aimed to explain how the selective inclusion of minority figures in decision-making bodies served to justify that corrective actions were being undertaken (Moss Kanter, 1979). Thus, women or black individuals in such roles became tokens representing their groups, while the underlying issues of underrepresentation and inequality persisted. Since then, these theories have gained broad acceptance and have been applied across various fields to describe strategies of simulated participation (Di Santo, Lopolito, & Sisto, 2023).

Various studies of environmental behavioral dissonance have identified tokenism as a cognitive strategy used to reduce tension and restore consonance. Tokenism involves individuals citing specific, often superficial, environmentally responsible behaviors to justify their overall environmental behavior. As Gifford (2011) has suggested, these justificatory behaviors may be easy to perform but have minimal environmental impact, while the behaviors individuals forego are often more difficult but have a greater positive effect. This nuance has led Gifford and Chen (2016, p. 11) to define tokenism as 'sub-consequential efforts for the environment that preclude more impactful actions.

Several studies have highlighted the role of tokenism in environmental behaviours. Bosone, Chevrier, and Zenasni (2022) have shown that the recollection of past pro-

environmental conduct enables individuals to alleviate psychological tension and to perpetuate the notion that they have already contributed enough. Gupta et al. (2021) have identified tokenism as a major psychological hurdle preventing tourists from adopting environmentally responsible behaviours during their trips. Furthermore, Vieira, Castro, & Souza (2023) have revealed that tokenism constitutes the second most substantial barrier hindering the translation of pro-environmental attitudes into concrete climate change mitigation actions.

Tokenism may alleviate cognitive tension regarding environmental behaviours through several mechanisms. For example, a few pro-environmental actions can lead to a 'halo effect,' reducing scrutiny of less sustainable behaviours (Bosone et al., 2022). Similarly, in goal-oriented individuals, tokenism may divert attention from broader, more demanding goals (Geng et al., 2016). Additionally, easily achievable environmental actions can serve as justifications for unsustainable behaviours (Langseth and Viff, 2021). Finally, individuals may employ a 'generic evaluation' of their behaviours, avoiding specific scrutiny of harmful actions (Schrems & Upham, 2020).

Complementing tokenism theories, a substantial body of research has examined the influence of perceived costs on pro-environmental behaviour. Studies have consistently demonstrated that individuals are more likely to overcome self-interest when they are involved in low-cost situations (Harrell, 2021). In terms of environmental behaviours, such actions are more often developed when the associated costs are perceived as low (Diekmann & Preisendörfer, 2003; Busche & Sargisson, 2020). Conversely, high perceived costs can act as a barrier, hindering the translation of pro-environmental attitudes into action (Moore & Boldero, 2017). While some studies suggest that environmental values (Best, 2009), or certain institutional actions may enable individuals to overcome high-cost situations (Rompf, Kroneberg & Schlösser, 2017), evidence continues to support the significance of these barriers in triggering environmentally responsible behaviours.

This paper delves deeper into these findings, examining the degree of consistency between individuals' general self-assessments of their environmental behaviours and the specific behaviours they engage in. As previously proposed, when assessing environmentally responsible conduct, it is essential to examine specific behavioral domains that manifest such conduct (Diekmann & Preisendörfer, 1998). The study seeks to validate two hypotheses. Firstly, in line with the literature that highlights significant discrepancies between individuals' self-evaluations and their actual environmental behaviours, we hypothesize that:

H1. A striking discrepancy exists between individuals' general self-assessments of their environmental behaviours, as evidenced by high levels of agreement with the statement 'I always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer', and a much lower reported frequency of the following specific pro-environmental behaviours:

- Reduced number or return flights in the past 12 months.
- Reduced number of ours spent in private motor vehicles.
- Reduced number of days a week eating meat.
- High frequency of waste separation.
- High frequency of consumption reduction due to environmental concerns.
- Participation in environmental organizations

- Signed petitions for environmental issues.
- Donations to environmental organizations.
- Participation in environmental demonstrations.

Secondly, assuming 1) the literature evidence of a higher probability of resolving cognitive dissonance in environmental matters through the manipulation of cognitive elements, 2) the propensity to make generic assessments of one's own behaviour, rather than closely inspecting specific behaviours, 3) the likelihood of resorting to tokenism as a strategy for resolving environmental cognitive dissonance, and 4) the likelihood that behaviours requiring a lower cost are the ones that are actually activated in environmental protection, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2. Individuals who engage in more frequent, low-cost pro-environmental behaviours, such as:

- High frequency of waste separation.
 - High frequency of consumption reduction due to environmental concerns.
- are more likely to report that they 'always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer'. This suggests a strategy of reducing cognitive dissonance on environmental issues, based on tokenism.

To test the second hypothesis, it was examined the extent to which specific pro-environmental behaviours enhanced the prediction of individuals to positively self-assess their general environmental behaviours. These specific behaviours were contrasted with other variables known from the literature to influence pro-environmental behaviour. These control variables included:

- Gender: with women more likely to engage in pro-environmental behaviours (Smith & Brower, 2012; Rothberger, 2020).
- Age: with older populations exhibiting higher levels of such behaviours (Asvatourian et al., 2018; Tobler, Visschers, & Siegrist, 2012).
- Education: with higher education levels linked to more sustainable behaviours (Kollmus & Agyeman, 2002; Schrems & Upham, 2020).
- Income: with higher incomes associated with more pro-environmental behaviours (Ertz, Karakas, & Sarigollu, 2016; Bronfman et al., 2015).
- Ideology: with left-leaning individuals exhibiting more pro-environmental behaviours (Cheung et al., 2019; Franzel & Vogl, 2013).
- Climate change denial: which reduces pro-environmental behaviours (Gifford & Chen, 2016; Lacroix, Gifford, & Chen, 2019).
- Perceived importance of environmental problems: which increases pro-environmental behaviours (Thøgersen, 2004; Whitmarsh et al., 2022).
- Exposure to the effects of climate change: which increases pro-environmental behaviours (Shinan-Altman & Hamama-Raz, 2023).
- Personal efficacy: with higher levels increasing pro-environmental behaviours (Broom, 2017; Ertz, Karakas, & Sarigollu, 2016).
- Pro-environmental attitudes: which enhance pro-environmental behaviours (Barr & Gilg, 2007; Lavergne & Pelletier, 2015).

3. Data and Methods.

This study is based on a secondary statistical analysis of the Spanish General Social Survey, Environment Module, conducted by the Centre for Sociological Research (CIS)

in 2023. The survey was administered to a nationally representative sample of 2,254 individuals, selected through a stratified sampling procedure. This design allows for estimates with a margin of error of +/-2.1% and a 95.5% confidence level.

Statistical analysis involved generating descriptive analyses to observe the distribution of environmentally responsible behaviours among the population. To address the first hypothesis, the prevalence of specific behaviours was examined, as well as a generic self-assessment of overall behaviour, summarised by the statement: 'I always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer'. Furthermore, cross-tabulations were conducted to explore how the presence of other specific environmentally responsible behaviours was distributed within this self-assessment. To determine the significance of the results, Chi-squared tests were conducted for ordinal and nominal variables, and Student's t-tests were used to assess the significance of mean differences for numerical variables.

Subsequently, to test the second hypothesis, a series of logistic regressions were conducted to estimate the probability of individuals positive self-assessment of overall environmental behaviour, as a function of different values taken by various predictor variables. The first model included control variables that the literature has identified as being frequently associated with environmentally responsible behaviours, as previously noted. In the second model, specific environmentally responsible behaviours were introduced, with the aim of determining whether they produced significant improvements in the predictive power of the variance of the dependent variable. The characteristics of the variables used in the different statistical tests are presented in the following table.

Table 1: Variables Used in the Analysis

Variable	Level	Values
Level of agreement "I always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer".	Ordinal	Completely disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, completely agree.
Return flights in the past 12 months	Numerical	0-70
Hours spent in private motor vehicles	Numerical	0-90
Days a week eating meat	Numerical	0-7
Frequency of waste separation	Ordinal	Never, occasionally, frequently, always.
Frequency of consumption reduction due to environmental concerns: Always	Ordinal	Never, occasionally, frequently, always.
Members of environmental organizations	Nominal	Yes, no
People who signed petitions for environmental issues	Nominal	Yes, no
People who made donations to environmental organizations	Nominal	Yes, no
Participants in environmental demonstrations	Nominal	Yes, no
Sex	Nominal	Men, women
Age	Numerical	18-97

Years of schooling	Numerical	1-30
Hosehold saving capacity (Scale)	Ordinal	We have incurred debts in the last month, We have dipped into our savings in the last month, We're living paycheck to paycheck, We save some money each month, We save a lot of money each month.
Scale of ideological orientation	Ordinal	0 (left)-10 (right)
Conviction about climate change	Nominal	It has not changed, it has changed due to natural cycles, it has changed due to natural cycles and human activity, it has changed due to human activity
Level of agreement "Other issues should take precedence over environmental protection"	Ordinal	Completely agree, agree, neutral, disagree, completely disagree
Scale of environmental concern	Ordinal	1 I don't care- 5 I'm very worried
Level of agreement: "Environmental issues have a direct impact on my daily life"	Ordinal	Completely agree, agree, neutral, disagree, completely disagree
Level of agreement: "I find it difficult to know whether my lifestyle is good or bad for the environment"	Ordinal	Completely agree, agree, neutral, disagree, completely disagree
Level of agreement: "It's very difficult for someone like me to make a difference for the environment"	Ordinal	Completely agree, agree, neutral, disagree, completely disagree
Level of agreement: "I support the idea of paying much higher prices to ensure environmental protection"	Ordinal	Completely disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, completely agree
Level of agreement: "I support the idea of paying much higher taxes to ensure environmental protection"	Ordinal	Completely disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, completely agree
Level of agreement: "I support the idea of accepting a lower standard of living to protect the environment"	Ordinal	Completely disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, completely agree

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

In the logistic regression models, Likert scale variables were treated as numerical variables.

4. Results.

Table 2. Prevalence of Sustainable Behaviours.

Sustainability behaviour	Percentage
"I always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer" Response options: Agree or completely agree	55.38%
How many return flights have you taken in the past 12 months? Response options: No one	59.45%

In a typical week, how many hours do you spend driving or riding in a car, motorbike, van, or lorry, not including time on buses or trains? Response options: One or less	36.30%
In a typical week how many days a week do you eat beef, lamb, or meat-based products? Response options: No one	18.86%
How frequently do you take the time to separate glass, cans, plastic, paper, and other materials for recycling? Response options: Always	61.84%
How frequently do you avoid purchasing certain products for environmental reasons? Response options: Always	8.81%
Are you a member of any group or organization whose primary objective is to conserve or protect the environment? Response option: Yes	3.49%
In the past five years, have you signed any petitions relating to environmental issues? Response option: Yes	26.03%
In the last five years, have you made any donations to environmental organizations? Response option: No	9.81%
Have you participated in an environmental protest or demonstration in the past five years? Response option: No	11.64%

Source: Authors' calculation based on the Spanish General Social Survey (CIS)

Table 2 reveals a significant disparity between respondents' self-assessed pro-environmental behaviour and their participation in specific eco-friendly actions. While 55.38% of participants asserted they were making maximal efforts to protect the environment, only two concrete behaviours—avoiding flights and consistent recycling—exceeded this general claim. Conversely, donations to environmental organizations, reduced consumption, and membership in environmental groups were reported at considerably lower rates, suggesting a discrepancy between self-assessment and actual practice (see Table 2).

To further examine the relationship between the general self-assessment about environmental protection and specific pro-environmental behaviours, a cross-tabulation was conducted (Table 3). A chi-squared analysis was conducted to examine associations between nominal and ordinal variables. All associations were statistically significant, with the exception of that between self-assessment of environmental behaviour and membership in environmental organizations ($p = 0.133$). To compare mean differences in numerical variables and the generic self-assessment of environmental behaviour, independent t-tests were employed. Significant differences were observed between this self-assessment and weekly meat consumption ($p = 0.001$), but not between this self-assessment and the number of flights or hours spent in private motor vehicles ($p = 0.558$, 0.139 , respectively).

Table 3. Prevalence of specific pro-environmental behaviours, as reported by individuals claiming to do everything possible to protect the environment.

Particular behaviours	"I always try to do what's best for the environment". Response: YES		"I always try to do what's best for the environment". Response: NO	
	Percentages	Average	Percentages	Average
Return flights in the past 12 months		1.76		1.62
Hours spent in private motor vehicles		4.37		4.90
Days a week eating meat		1.77		2.01

Frequency of waste separation: Always	74.53%		47.75%	
Frequency of consumption reduction due to environmental concerns: Always	11.87%		4.89%	
Members of environmental organizations	4.28%		2.50%	
People who signed petitions for environmental issues	32.68%		19.66%	
People who made donations to environmental organizations	13.82%		5.06%	
Participants in environmental demonstrations	15.17%		7.93%	

Source: Authors' calculation based on the Spanish General Social Survey (CIS)

Table 3 indicates that self-assessment of the general behaviour to protect the environment was not consistently associated with the presence of effective pro-environmental behaviours. While a high proportion of individuals who assessed their general behaviour positively reported consistently separating domestic waste (74.53%), other actions were less prevalent. For instance, among those who positively self-assessed their general environmental behaviour, 32.68% had signed petitions, 15.17% had participated in demonstrations, 13.82% had made donations to environmental organisations, 11.87% always reduced consumption for environmental reasons, and 4.28% had belonged to an environmental organisation. Furthermore, there were no significant mean differences in some specific behaviours based on general self-assessment. For example, the mean number of flights in the past 12 months was higher among those who positively self-assessed their general environmental behaviour (1.76 flights) compared to those who did not (1.62 flights). The average weekly hours spent in private motor vehicles and the average number of days per week eating meat were 4.37 hours and 1.77 times, respectively, among those who positively self-assessed their general environmental behaviour, while these figures were not substantially higher among those who did not (Table 3).

Various logistic regression models were employed to investigate the presence of tokenism in self-assessed favourable general environmental behaviour. Specifically, these models sought to identify specific behaviours that could serve as tokens for this general behaviour. Sociodemographic and attitudinal variables, identified in the literature as potential influences on the formation of environmentally responsible behaviours, were included as control variables in a first step. In a second step, effective environmental protection behaviours were introduced to determine whether the presence of any of

these behaviours was decisive in improving the likelihood of subjects confirming that they were doing everything they could to protect the environment.

Model 1, which included only control variables, accounted for between 19.6% (Cox and Snell R-squared) and 26.3% (Nagelkerke R-squared) of the variance in the dependent variable. This initial model was statistically significant, $\chi^2 (14, N= 1021) = 222.673$, $p < 0.001$, indicating its ability to accurately distinguish between individuals who reported favourable self-assessments of their generic environmental behaviours and those who did not. The model correctly classified 69.0% of cases. Model 2 additionally included all specific pro-environmental behaviours as potential predictors. The explanatory power of the second model increased, accounting for between 25.4% (Cox and Snell R-squared) and 34.1% (Nagelkerke R-squared) of the variance in reporting a general positive self-assessment. The second model, including all variables, was also significant, $\chi^2 (23, N = 1021) = 299.036$, $p < 0.001$, thus enabling accurate discrimination between those who reported that they have tried to do what was best for the environment. The second model correctly classified 72.1% of all cases.

To enhance the conciseness of the presentation, only the results of the second model are presented, as it integrates the factors of interest: effective environmental protection behaviours. These results are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. Logistic regression to explain the probability of reporting I always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer.

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp (B)
Men	0.284	0.158	3.245	1	0.072	1.329
Age	0.017	0.005	10.318	1	0.001	1.017
Years of schooling	0.004	0.017	0.053	1	0.818	1.004
Household saving capacity (Scale)	-0.046	0.079	0.338	1	0.561	0.955
Scale of ideological orientation	0.034	0.032	1.130	1	0.288	1.034
Climate change is either nonexistent or caused by natural cycles	-0.465	0.353	1.735	1	0.188	0.628
Other issues should take precedence over environmental protection (Scale of agreement)	0.076	0.078	0.937	1	0.333	1.079
Scale of environmental concern	0.097	0.104	0.872	1	0.350	1.102
Environmental issues have a direct impact on my daily life (Scale of agreement)	0.198	0.084	5.500	1	0.019	1.219
I find it difficult to know whether my lifestyle is good or bad for the environment (Scale of agreement)	0.180	0.081	4.947	1	0.026	1.197
It's very difficult for someone like me to make a difference for the environment (Scale of agreement)	0.071	0.074	0.910	1	0.340	1.073
I support the idea of paying much higher prices to ensure environmental protection (Scale of agreement)	0.070	0.112	0.387	1	0.534	1.072
I support the idea of paying much higher taxes to ensure environmental protection (Scale of agreement)	0.189	0.111	2.910	1	0.088	1.209

I support the idea of accepting a lower standard of living to protect the environment (Scale of agreement)	0.257	0.089	8.403	1	0.004	1.292
Return flights in the past 12 months	0.007	0.012	0.327	1	0.567	1.007
Hours spent in private motor vehicles	-0.011	0.009	1.384	1	0.239	0.989
Days a week eating meat	0.095	0.052	3.420	1	0.064	1.100
Frequency of waste separation (Scale)	0.393	0.089	19.330	1	0.000	1.481
Frequency of consumption reduction due to environmental concerns (Scale)	0.501	0.105	22.835	1	0.000	1.650
Members of environmental organizations	-0.227	0.457	0.247	1	0.619	0.797
Signed petitions for environmental issues	-0.042	0.184	0.052	1	0.819	0.959
Made donations to environmental organizations	0.677	0.302	5.006	1	0.025	1.967
Participated in environmental demonstrations	0.223	0.262	0.727	1	0.394	1.250
Constant	-5.382	0.803	44.929	1	0.000	0.005

Source: Authors' calculation based on the Spanish General Social Survey (CIS)

Of the control variables only four were significant in explaining the dependent variable. Among these, the strongest determinant was the degree of agreement with the statement: "I support the idea of accepting a lower standard of living to protect the environment". For each unit increase in agreement with this statement, the odds of reporting trying to do what's best for the environment increased by a factor of 1.292. Similar effects were observed for agreement with 'Environmental issues directly impact my daily life' (odds ratio: 1.212) and reduced disagreement with 'I find it difficult to assess my lifestyle's environmental impact' (odds ratio: 1.197). Age was also a significant predictor, with each additional year increasing the odds of the positive self-assessment of behaviour by 1.017.

The preceding cross-sectional analysis revealed considerable variability in the overlap between specific environmentally responsible behaviours and individuals' self-assessment of doing everything they could for the environment. This substantial variability is also evident when examining how these specific behaviours constitute determinants of such self-assessment. Indeed, a great number of these specific behaviours were non-significant, such as the number of flights taken, hours spent travelling in private motor vehicles, weekly meat consumption, membership of environmental organisations, having signed petitions for environmental protection, or participation in environmental protests. These behaviours were not considered by subjects when positively self-assessing their overall environmental protection behaviour. Conversely, other specific behaviours were shown to determine this self-assessment. In fact, of all the factors considered, including control variables, making donations to environmental organisations, reducing consumption for environmental reasons, and the frequency of household waste separation were the factors that most strongly determined individuals' recognition of doing everything that was good to protect the environment. The presence of these specific behaviours multiplied by 1.967 times, 1.650 times, and 1.481 times, respectively, the probability that subjects would make this general assessment of their behaviour.

5. Discussion.

The findings revealed a significant variability in the frequency of specific environmentally responsible behaviours and the self-assessment of the general pro-environmental behaviour. Notably, a substantial majority (55.38%) claimed to do everything they could to protect the environment. However, the specific behaviours presented a more nuanced picture, with only 3.49% actively participating in environmental organizations, 8.81% avoiding purchasing products for environmental reasons, and 18.86% abstaining from meat consumption on a weekly basis.

The overlap between self-assessed generic environmental behaviour and the presence of specific pro-environmental behaviours allowed us, in a second step, to confirm almost all elements of Hypothesis 1. It was found that, among those who indicated doing everything possible to protect the environment, there was a notable absence of several crucial behaviours to promote such protection, such as reducing consumption for environmental reasons (only 11.87% of individuals), being a member of environmental organisations (4.28%), signing petitions for environmental protection (32.88%), making donations for this purpose (13.82%), or participating in environmental demonstrations (15.17%). Furthermore, there were no differences in behaviours such as the number of annual flights, weekly hours spent in private motor vehicles, or weekly meat consumption between those who indicated doing everything they could to protect the environment and those who did not. The only exception to this discrepancy was the behaviour of waste separation, as a high percentage of subjects who reported doing everything possible to protect the environment engaged in this practice. Consequently, the research confirms Hypothesis 1, which posited a marked divergence between subjects' self-assessment of environmental care, expressed by high levels of agreement with the statement 'I always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer', and a much lower presence of the following behaviours:

- Reduced number or return flights in the past 12 months.
- Reduced number of hours spent in private motor vehicles.
- Reduced number of days a week eating meat.
- High frequency of waste separation.
- Participation in environmental organizations
- Signed petitions for environmental issues.
- Donations to environmental organizations.
- Participation in environmental demonstrations.

These findings corroborate previous research indicating limited overlap between specific pro-environmental behaviours in certain groups (Langseth & Vyff, 2021; Thøgersen, 2004). Moreover, they confirm the observed discrepancy between highly favourable self-assessments of environmental behaviour and the presence of specific behaviours, many of which may be detrimental to the environment (Schrems & Upham, 2020).

Logistic regression analyses revealed that including specific pro-environmental behaviours significantly improved the prediction of self-assessed general environmental behaviour beyond that provided by control variables. While the control variables accounted for 19.6% (Cox and Snell R^2) to 26.3% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in self-assessed general behaviour, the inclusion of specific behaviours increased this explanatory power to 25.4% and 34.1%, respectively. Moreover, examination of the

coefficients of determination indicated that only a few specific pro-environmental behaviours were significantly associated with a positive self-assessment of general environmental behaviour. These included making donations to environmental organizations, reducing consumption for environmental reasons, and frequent household waste separation. Consistent with previous research (Tobler, Visschers, & Siegrist, 2012), these behaviours tend to involve lower costs for individuals. In contrast, other behaviours, such as reducing air travel, private car use, meat consumption, or participation in environmental groups, were not significantly associated with self-assessed general environmental behaviour. The literature consistently identifies such behaviours as being more costly (Lane & Poter, 2007; Tobler, Visschers & Siegrist, 2012; Kriwy & Mecking, 2012).

These findings provide partial support for Hypothesis 2, indicating that Individuals who engage in more frequent, low-cost pro-environmental behaviours, such as:

- High frequency of waste separation.

- High frequency of consumption reduction due to environmental concerns.

- Donations to environmental organizations

are more likely to report that they 'always try to do what's best for the environment, even if it means spending more money or taking longer'. The final assertion only includes, with respect to the initially proposed Hypothesis 2, the behaviour of "Making donations to environmental organizations".

These findings contribute to the growing body of literature highlighting the role of tokenism in reducing cognitive dissonance related to environmentally responsible behaviours. In particular, they corroborate previous research indicating a preference for low-cost pro-environmental behaviours at the expense of more costly, yet impactful, actions (Gifford & Chen, 2017; Fishbach, Dhar, & Zhang, 2006). Our results introduced a novel dimension to these arguments, suggesting that tokenistic behaviours influence individuals' positive self-assessment of their overall environmental performance. Such greater satisfaction with their general environmental behaviour can prevent individuals from adopting additional, more impactful actions. Given these findings, a key challenge in mitigating environmental damage is to develop strategies that disrupt this complacency and encourage individuals to shift from low-cost tokenistic behaviours toward more costly but effective actions (Vieira, Castro, & Souza, 2023).

This study relied on the analysis of existing databases from the Centre for Sociological Research. Consequently, it was unable to explicitly incorporate a range of other variables that would have been crucial for assessing the intensity of cognitive dissonance in subjects, according to the presence of different independent variables. To address this limitation, it would be necessary to design surveys specifically to introduce these determinants and to develop experimental strategies that could reveal such variability. Furthermore, there is a need to generate new knowledge demonstrating the specific conditions under which individuals can deactivate the performance of other behaviours of greater relevance for environmental protection. This would require accumulating both experimental and qualitative research.

Declaration of conflicting interest

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

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